

Examination of Self and Decision Making Levels of Students Receiving Education in Schools of Physical Education and Sports

Mustafa Yildiz, Murat Tekin, Hasan Şahan, Ahmet Şahin, Mehmet Şaker, Buket Ulucan, Osman Mutlu

Abstract—The purpose of this study is to examine the self and decision making levels of students receiving education in schools of physical training and sports. The population of the study consisted 258 students, among which 152 were male and 106 were female (\bar{X} age=19,3713 \pm 1,6968), that received education in the schools of physical education and sports of Selcuk University, Inonu University, Gazi University and Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University. In order to achieve the purpose of the study, the Melbourne Decision Making Questionnaire developed by Mann et al. (1998) [1] and adapted to Turkish by Deniz (2004) [2] and the Self-Esteem Scale developed by Aricak (1999) [3] was utilized. For analyzing and interpreting data Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, t-test and one way anova test were used, while for determining the difference between the groups Tukey test and Multiple Linear Regression test were employed and significance was accepted at $P < 0.05$. SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) package software was used for evaluating the data and finding out the calculated values. In conclusion of the present study, while cautious, avoidant and postponing decision making levels of male students were found out to be higher than female students, panic decision making levels of female students were found out to be higher than that of male students. While cautious, avoidant and panic-driven decision making levels of the students attending to the first grade were found out to be higher than these of the fourth grades, for the students attending to the fourth grade influential decision making levels were found out to be higher. While male students were found out to be having relatively higher self value, self confidence and self sufficiency levels, for female students achieving, productivity and depressive affect were found out to be higher in comparison with male students. While self values, achieving and productivity levels of the students attending to the first grade were found out to be higher than those of fourth grade students, fourth grade students were determined to have higher self-confidence, depressive affection and self-sufficiency levels. It was also determined that there is a significant relation between decision making levels and self levels.

Keywords—Physical Education And Sports, Student, Self, Decision Making

I. INTRODUCTION

AN individual makes definitions about himself/herself by discovering his/her own characteristics and attitudes and through the feedbacks from other individuals. If an individual defines himself/herself as an individual equipped with positive characteristics, he/she has a high self-esteem level. On the other hand, if an individual has negative and conflicting perceptions about himself/herself, he/she has a low self-esteem level. Judgments of an individual about himself/herself and perceptions about whether he/she is apt for the standards he/she wants to attain determines self-esteem.

Mustafa Yildiz Murat Tekin Hasan Şahan Ahmet Şahin Mehmet Şaker Buket Ulucan are with Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University School of Physical Education and Sports Karaman, Turkey (corresponding e-mail : murattekin76@gmail.com)

Osman Mutlu is with Mugla University School of Physical Education and Sports Mugla, Turkey

In interpersonal relationships, individuals tend to choose people like them or those who will approve and support them. Supportive relationships also support self-esteem of individuals. Individuals, who tend to choose people suitable for themselves, try to choose and create environments which are appropriate for them. Efforts and attempts supporting his/her socialization and honoring him/her will also increase self-respect. Individuals make decisions of varying degrees of importance every day.

Thus, decision-making may not seem so complicated at first. However, decision-making involves a process in which strong and weak aspects of the individual is interconnected. By understanding what decision-making concerns, individuals can be helped to make more reliable decisions. Understanding of decision-making process is important due to its practical benefits in explaining the elements of the process. Decision-making styles are one of the important reasons for individual differences in the process.

Decision-making studies give a priority focus on how to decide and what to take as a basis for decision making [4-5]. Self-esteem, which is the combination of perception, emotion and ideas important to an individual and is significant in terms of personality development, plays an important role in socialization level of individuals [6]. Accordingly, always having expectations and being in search of new things make the individuals encounter difficulties in using their decision-making strategies. For this reason, decision-making approach of the individual and the strategies and styles he/she employs in decision making behavior gain importance. An individual should be helped to acquire appropriate and effective decision making skills for life satisfaction and self-development [7]. Teachers should try to educate individuals with a high adaptation level. To enhance self-esteem levels of students, teachers should establish a close relationship with the students at least to avoid lowering their existing self-esteem levels.

II. METHOD

A. Research group

The population of the study consisted 258 students, among which 152 were male and 106 were female (\bar{X} age=19,3713 \pm 1,6968), that received education in the schools of physical education and sports of Selcuk University, Inonu University, Gazi University and Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University.

B. Data Collection

In order to achieve the purpose of the study, the Melbourne Decision Making Questionnaire developed by Mann et al. (1998) [1] and adapted to Turkish by Deniz (2004) [2] and the Self-Esteem Scale developed by Aricak (1999) [3] was utilized.

C. Analysis of Data

For analyzing and interpreting data Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, t-test and one way anova test were used, while for determining the difference between the groups Tukey test and Multiple Linear Regression test were employed and significance was accepted at $P < 0.05$. SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) package software was used for evaluating the data and finding out the calculated values.

III. FINDINGS

TABLE I
T TEST RESULTS OF DECISION-MAKING LEVELS OF THE STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACCORDING TO GENDER VARIABLE

		N	Mean	Std. Deviat	t	p
Vigilant Decision-Making	Male	1	18,14	2,49	-6,4	0,0
	Female	1	16,34	1,73		
Buckpassing	Male	1	21,03	3,25	-3,1	0,0
	Female	1	19,82	2,84		
Procrastinatin Decision-Making	Male	1	15,07	2,83	-3,1	0,0
	Female	1	14,01	2,56		
Hypervigilant Decision-Making	Male	1	14,95	2,46	-3,7	0,0
	Female	1	16,19	2,75		

As indicated in Table I, there was a significant difference between decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender [t value = -6.428 $P = 0.000 < 0.05$]. Average values showed that vigilant decision-making level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 18.1415$) while vigilant decisions-making level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 16.3421$).

- It was found that there was a significant difference between buckpassing decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender [t value = -3.105 $P = 0.002 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that buckpassing decision-making level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 21.0377$) while buckpassing decision-making level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 19.8224$).
- It was found that there was a significant difference between procrastinating decision-making level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [t value = -3.137 $P = 0.002 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that procrastinating decision-making level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 15.0755$) while procrastinating decision-making level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 14.0132$).
- It was found that there was a significant difference between hypervigilant decision-making level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender [t value = -3.794 $P = 0.000 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that hypervigilant decision-making level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 14.9539$) while hypervigilant

decision-making level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 16.1981$).

TABLE II
T TEST RESULTS OF SELF-ESTEEM LEVELS OF THE STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACCORDING TO GENDER VARIABLE

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p
self-esteem	Male	152	27,1698	2,6131	-1,430	0,044
	Female	106	26,7039	2,2571		
self-confidence	Male	152	27,1509	2,0876	-1,883	0,037
	Female	106	26,9079	2,2327		
depressed affect	Male	152	17,7368	1,8584	-3,221	0,002
	Female	106	18,6226	2,3683		
achievement and productivity	Male	152	19,7830	1,7458	2,002	0,046
	Female	106	20,2368	1,8224		
self-sufficiency	Male	152	10,9539	2,8316	-1,738	0,043
	Female	106	11,4717	1,9528		

As indicated in Table II, there was a significant difference between self-esteem levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [t value = -1.430 $P = 0.044 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that self-esteem level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 27.1698$) while self-esteem levels of female students was ($\bar{X} = 26.7039$).

- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-confidence level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [t value = -1.883 $P = 0.037 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that self-confidence level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 27.1509$) while self-confidence level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 26.9079$).
- It was found that there was a significant difference between depressed affect level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender [t value = -3.221 $P = 0.002 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that depressed affect level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 17.7368$) while depressed affect level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 18.6226$).
- It was found that there was a significant difference between achievement and productivity level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [t value = 2.002 $P = 0.046 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that achievement and productivity level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 19.7830$) while achievement and productivity level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 20.2368$).
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-sufficiency levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender [t value = -1.738 $P = 0.043 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that self-sufficiency level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 10.9539$) while self-sufficiency level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 11.4717$).

TABLE III

ONE WAY ANOVA RESULTS OF DECISION-MAKING LEVELS OF THE STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACCORDING TO GRADE LEVEL VARIABLE

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P	tukey test
Vigilant Decision-Making	Between Groups	47,290	3	15,763	3,178	0,025	1-4
	Within Groups	1260,000	254	4,961			
	Total	1307,291	257				
Buckpassing	Between Groups	127,943	3	42,648	4,713	0,003	1-4
	Within Groups	2298,356	254	9,049			
	Total	2426,298	257				
Procrastinating Decision-Making	Between Groups	7,309	3	2,436	1,326	0,048	4-1
	Within Groups	1896,536	254	7,467			
	Total	1903,845	257				
Hypervigilant Decision-Making	Between Groups	140,741	3	46,914	7,112	0,000	1-4
	Within Groups	1675,445	254	6,596			
	Total	1816,186	257				

As indicated in Table III, there was a significant difference between vigilant decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [F value = 3.178 P=0.025<0.05]. It was found that 1.grade students had higher vigilant decision-making levels than 4.grade students.

- It was found that there was a significant difference between buckpassing decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 4.713 P=0.003<0.05]. It was found that 1.grade students had higher buckpassing decision-making levels than 4.grade students.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between procrastinating decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 1.326 P=0.048<0.05]. Procrastinating decision-making levels of 4.grade students were found to be higher than those of 1.grade students.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between hypervigilant decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 7.112 P=0.000<0.05]. 1.grade students were found to have higher hypervigilant decision-making levels than 4.grade students.

TABLE IV

ONE WAY ANOVA RESULTS OF SELF-ESTEEM LEVELS OF THE STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACCORDING TO GRADE LEVEL VARIABLE

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	tukey test
self-esteem	Between Groups	8,591	3	2,864	1,427	0,033	1-4
	Within Groups	1701,583	254	6,699			
	Total	1710,174	257				
self-confidence	Between Groups	23,037	3	7,679	2,638	0,018	4-1
	Within Groups	1190,948	254	4,689			
	Total	1213,984	257				
depressed affect	Between Groups	4,761	3	1,587	1,349	0,049	4-1
	Within Groups	1154,619	254	4,546			
	Total	1159,380	257				
achievement and productivity	Between Groups	16,338	3	5,446	2,691	0,016	1-4
	Within Groups	818,007	254	3,220			
	Total	834,345	257				
self-sufficiency	Between Groups	5,752	3	1,917	1,300	0,048	4-1
	Within Groups	1622,081	254	6,386			
	Total	1627,833	257				

As indicated in Table IV, there was a significant difference between self-esteem level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 1.427 P=0.033<0.05]. It was found that 1.grade students had higher self-esteem levels than 4.grade students.

- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-confidence levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports [F value = 2.638 P=0.018<0.05]. 4.grade students were found to have higher self-confidence levels than 1.grade students.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between depressed affect levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level [F value = 1.349 P=0.049<0.05]. 4.grade students were found to have higher depressed affect levels than 1.grade students.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between achievement and productivity levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 2.691 P=0.016<0.05]. 1.grade students were found to have higher achievement and productivity level than 4.grade students.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-sufficiency levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 1.300 P=0.048<0.05]. 4.grade students were found to have higher self-sufficiency levels than 1. grade students.

TABLE V
CORRELATION ANALYSIS BETWEEN SELF-ESTEEM AND DECISION-MAKING LEVELS OF THE STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

		self-esteem	self-confidence	depressed affect	achievement and productivity	self-sufficiency
Vigilant Decision-Making	r	0.339	0.071	0.309	-0.048	-0.242
	p	0.000	0.259	0.000	0.446	0.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
Buckpassing	r	0.192	0.019	-0.069	0.059	-0.289
	p	0.002	0.756	0.271	0.341	0.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
Procrastinating Decision-Making	r	0.095	0.131	0.291	-0.024	-0.124
	p	0.126	0.036	0.000	0.701	0.046
	N	258	258	258	258	258
Hypervigilant Decision-Making	r	-0.108	0.372	-0.017	0.360	-0.316
	p	0.083	0.000	0.782	0.000	0.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258

As indicated in Table V, there was a positive significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and self-esteem levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports ($r=0.339$ $p<0.05$).

- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and self-confidence levels ($r=0.071$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and depressed affect levels ($r=0.309$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($r=-0.048$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($r=0.242$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and self-esteem levels ($r=0.192$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and self-confidence levels ($r=0.019$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and depressed affect levels ($r=0.069$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($r=-0.059$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($r=0.289$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and self-esteem levels ($r=0.095$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and self-confidence levels ($r=0.131$ $p<0.05$).

- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and depressed affect levels ($r=0.291$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($r=-0.024$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($r=-0.124$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and self-esteem levels ($r=0.108$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and self-confidence levels ($r=0.372$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and depressed affect levels ($r=0.017$ $p>0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($r=-0.360$ $p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($r=-0.316$ $p<0.05$).

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULT

- It was found that there was a significant difference between vigilant decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [$P<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had a vigilant decision-making level of ($\bar{X}=18.1415$) while female students had a vigilant decision-making level of ($\bar{X}=16.3421$). These results reveal that when compared to female students, male students meticulously search and evaluate necessary information before decision-making. The findings of the present study are consistent with the findings of Radford et al., (1993) [8], Leaper (1998) [9], Mann et al., (1998) [1].
- It was found that there was a significant difference between buckpassing decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable. Mean values showed that male students had a buckpassing decision-making level of ($\bar{X}=21.0377$) while female students had a buckpassing decision-making level of ($\bar{X}=19.8224$). These results reveal that when compared to female students, male students leave their decisions to other people and do not take responsibility. The findings of the present study are in parallel to the findings of Mau (2000) [10].
- It was found that there was a significant difference between procrastinating decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [$P<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had a procrastinating decision making level of ($\bar{X}=15.0755$) while female students had a

procrastinating decision-making level of ($\bar{X}=14.0132$). These results reveal that when compared to female students, male students delay all decisions without a valid reason.

- It was found that there was a significant difference between hypervigilant decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [$P<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had a hypervigilant decision-making level of ($\bar{X}=14.9539$) while female students had hypervigilant decision-making level of ($\bar{X}=16.1981$). These results show that when compared to female students, male students feel under time constraints and behave in an impetuous manner.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-esteem levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender [$P<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had a self-esteem level of ($\bar{X}=27.1698$) while female students had a self-esteem level of ($\bar{X}=26.7039$). These results reveal that when compared female students, male students value the characteristics they have or should have at a higher level. The findings of our study are consistent with the findings of Cairns (1990) [11], Ormond et al (1991) [12], Ohannessian and Eye (1999) [13].
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-confidence levels of the students studying in school of physical and education and sports according to gender variable [$p<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had a self-confidence level of ($\bar{X}=27.1509$) while female students had a self-confidence level of ($\bar{X}=26.9079$). These results reveal that when compared to female students, male students have a high level of attributing value to their characteristics and to approve themselves due to these characteristics.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between depressed affect levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [$p<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had a depressed affect level of ($\bar{X}=17.7368$) while female students had a depressed affect level of ($\bar{X}=18.6226$). These results show that when compared to male students, female students perceive themselves weaker and more desperate.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between achievement and productivity levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [$P<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had an achievement and productivity level of ($\bar{X}=19.7830$) while female students had an achievement and productivity level of ($\bar{X}=20.2368$). These results show that when compared to male students, female students perceive themselves as successful enough.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-sufficiency levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender variable [$P<0.05$]. Mean values showed that male students had a self-sufficiency level of ($\bar{X}=10.9539$) while female students had a self-sufficiency level of ($\bar{X}=11.4717$). Based on these results, it was observed that when compared to male students, female students had a higher level of realizing their expectations and objectives in mental and behavioral terms.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between vigilant decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. 1.grade students were found to have a higher vigilant decision-making level than 4.grade students. This indicates that 1.grade students evaluate alternatives in a vigilant manner. The findings of the present study are in parallel to the findings Burnet (1991) [14].
- It was found that there was a significant difference between buckpassing decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. Buckpassing decision-making level of 1.grade students was found to be higher than that of 4.grade students. This result indicates that 1.grade students tend to leave their decisions to other people and do not want to take responsibility. This might arise from the fact that they started school recently and could not adapt to the environment.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between procrastinating decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. 4.grade students were found to have a higher procrastinating decision-making level than 1.grade students. These results indicate that 4.grade students constantly procrastinate and delay their decisions. We believe that this might arise from the fact that they are senior students and under anxiety and stress.
- It was found that there was a significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. 1.grade students were found to have a higher hypervigilant decision-making level than 4.grade students. These results reveal that 1.grade students attempt to reach quick solutions.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-esteem levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports [$P<0.05$]. 1.grade students were found to have higher self-esteem level than 4.grade students. These results show that 1.grade students have varying cognitive, emotional and social levels. The findings of the present study are consistent with the findings of Francis and Jones (1996) [15], Hodges and Wolf (1997) [16].
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-confidence levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. 4.grade students were found to have a

higher self-confidence level than 1.grade students. These results show that 4.grade students have low self-esteem level and they cannot positively assess themselves.

- It was found that there was a significant difference between depressed affect levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. 4.grade students were found to have higher depressed affect levels than 1.grade students. We believe that this result arise from the problems concerning university possibilities, motivation levels and selection of profession.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between achievement and productivity levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. 1.grade students were found to have a higher achievement and productivity level than 4.grade students. We believe that this might result from the fact that 1.grade students started university quite recently; they fully trust and believe in themselves.
- It was found that there was a significant difference between self-sufficiency levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. 4.grade students were found to have a higher self-sufficiency level than 1.grade students. We believe that this might result from the fact that the individuals find themselves more positive and perceive themselves successful and beneficial enough.
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and self-esteem level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports ($p<0.05$). The findings of the present study are consistent with the findings of Hofstede (1999) [17], Burnett (1991) [14], Janis and Mann's (1979) [18], Amalor (1993) [19], Mann et al., (1989) [20], Ormond et al., (1991) [12], Ramanigopal (2008) [21].
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and self-confidence levels ($p>0.05$). There was a positive significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and depressed affect levels ($p<0.05$). It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($p>0.05$). There was a negative significant relationship between vigilant decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and self-esteem levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports ($p<0.05$). There was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and self-confidence levels ($p>0.05$). It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and depressed affect levels ($p>0.05$). There was a positive significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($p>0.05$). It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between buckpassing decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($p<0.05$).

- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and self-esteem levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports ($p>0.05$). There was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and self-confidence levels ($p<0.05$). It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and depressed affect levels ($p<0.05$). There was a positive significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($p>0.05$). It was found that there was a negative significant relationship between procrastinating decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($p<0.05$).
- It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and self-esteem levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports ($p<0.05$). There was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and self-confidence levels ($p<0.05$). It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and depressed affect levels ($p>0.05$). It was found that there was a positive significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and self-sufficiency levels ($p<0.05$). There was a negative significant relationship between hypervigilant decision-making and achievement and productivity levels ($p<0.05$).

In general terms, this present study indicates that self-esteem, which has an important role in personality development and is a whole of the perceptions, feelings and opinions important for the individual, also plays an important role on the socializing level of the individual. In this connection, being in constant expectation and always looking for something new, put individuals in a difficult situation at the point of using the decision making strategies they follow. This is why individuals' approach to decision making and the strategies and styles they implement while decision making gain importance. In order to get satisfaction from its life and develop itself, the individual needs assistance in gaining the skills of making the appropriate and effective decisions (Ersever, 1996). [7] It should be tried to raise individuals with high adaption levels by developing their interaction skills. It is necessary for the teachers to be close to their students and establish intimate relations with them in order to help them to increase their level of self-value, or at least maintain their self-esteem levels.

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